

Scalable Quantum Approximate Optimisers for Multi-Objective Optimisation (Appendix)

No Author Given

No Institute Given

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_x \mathcal{F}_*(x|\mathcal{W}, \mathcal{R}^*) &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq \mathcal{L}} \left\{ w_i |(x_i^T \mathcal{Q}_i x_i + x_i^T \mathcal{P}_i x_i) - r_i^*| \right\}, \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i = 1 \\
&= \max_{1 \leq i \leq \mathcal{L}} \left\{ |w_i (x_i^T \mathcal{Q}_i x_i + x_i^T \mathcal{P}_i x_i) - w_i r_i^*| \right\}, \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i > 0 \\
&= \max_{1 \leq i \leq \mathcal{L}} \left\{ |\mathcal{X}_i| \right\}, \mathcal{X}_i = w_i (x_i^T \mathcal{Q}_i x_i + x_i^T \mathcal{P}_i x_i) - w_i r_i^* \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} |\mathcal{X}_i|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, p \rightarrow \infty, (\ell^p \text{ norm properties [1]}) \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i^p |(x_i^T \mathcal{Q}_i x_i + x_i^T \mathcal{P}_i x_i) - r_i^*|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, (\ell^p \text{ homogeneity}) \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i^p |f_i(x) - r_i^*|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, f_i(x) = (x_i^T \mathcal{Q}_i x_i + x_i^T \mathcal{P}_i x_i) \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i^p \left(f_i(x) - r_i^* \right)^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \text{ when } p = 2k, k \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ and } k \rightarrow \infty \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i^p \sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} f_i(x)^j (-r_i^*)^{p-j} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, (\text{Binomial Expansion})
\end{aligned}$$

References

1. Marler, R., Arora, J.: Survey of multi-objective optimization methods for engineering. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* **26**, 369–395 (2004)